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Use, but verify

Composite Indices for Measuring the Information Society

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Abstract

The paper presents a brief examination of the use of composite indices in the analysis of information society issues. The main pros and cons are presented.

1 Introduction

None of the existing theories concerning the Information Society (IS) has solved any of the two following fundamental, connected – and probably insurmountable problems: definitional and measuring. There is no satisfying definition of the IS (Webster 2006). It entails a subsequent problem – how to measure almost an undefinable concept. The paper presents a short analysis of this „Grand Challenge” (Menou, Taylor 2006), focusing on composite indices (CI).

2 Measuring the Information Society

The presence of IS issues in public discourse in the last two decades has provoked a rising demand for tools allowing to quantify occurring processes. The main tools of quantitative description of IS are proper indices providing

information about different aspects of information and communication technologies (ICT) usage in society and economy. They are necessary in order to plan public and commercial projects and to assess their implementation. They are the essential part of development policies. Indices play a vital role in IS research. They measure, monitor and justify. A definitional function is essential – a specific index value may be used as a turning point, defining the formation of IS – which many critics have demanded for a long time. One should notice that constructing such indices is marked by certain partiality. It depends on the author's knowledge and intentions. The numerical expression of an indicator creates an impression of raw objectivity but its construction is often marked with subjective beliefs and purposes. Monitoring of IS requires the use of many molecular indicators. It seems that it is the only responsible way to monitor complex IS issues. This method is used by most "official" institutions, such as statistics offices, central government bodies or international organizations (e.g. Eurostat). Such research provides essential and thorough information. However, they also have a drawback of considerable importance. Many indicators in use are only clear to professionals. For others they are too hermetic, difficult and simply boring. Ongoing mediatization of our world has contributed to the popularization of a different research trend – composite indices (CI).

3 Composite Indices in IS Research

Composite indices enable a simpler interpretation of data. They substitute a large set of attributes with a single one – a synthetic variable. Transition from a multidimensional set of attributes to a one-dimensional is achieved by variable aggregation. What makes the CI so attractive is the fact that they are easy to interpret – the audience is presented with impressive rankings. CIs have become an essential part of the contemporary debate on social, economic, and political problems; and their popularity is still rising. A 2005 survey analyzed over 130 of such tools, 80% of which were created between years 1991 and 2005. During the 1970s and the 1980s less than 10 were created pro decade, in the 1990s – 40, and between 2000 and 2004 more than 60 (Bandura 2005). The 2008 survey analyzes almost 180 (Bandura 2008). This rising trend can be observed in the number of studies and in the variety of

authors. The scope of research is also constantly expanded, including virtually all contemporary and popular issues.

Many of the CIs have played a vital role in putting important issues in the centre of public attention and forcing policy-makers to act. Presently, it is difficult to imagine the discussions on development without the Human Development Index (UN), education without the PISA (OECD), corruption without the Corruption Perceptions Index (TI), competitiveness without the World Competitiveness Index (WEF) or, last but not least, IS without the Networked Readiness Index (also WEF). It seems plausible to put forward a thesis that if the authors stopped at the stage of drafting a large set of indicators and did not continue with the next stage, i.e. aggregation, the popularity of their research would suffer considerably. Moreover, the impact on the public would not have such serious consequences, i.e. people would be less involved and policy-makers wouldn't be forced to act.

CIs have an important political function. They mobilize people who are part of the decision making process and who did not participate in it earlier. According to Porter (2009: 11): "The indicators are objects that are constructed to maximize the aesthetic and exhortative effect of the representation of certain relationships while obscuring others". There are many arguments for and against using CIs (Bandura 2005: 13–14 and OECD 2008: 13–14). Arguments listed there should make one particularly wary when using CIs in IS analysis. One should bear in mind that the methodology used in creating a CI substantially influences the results and, correspondingly, the countries performance in a ranking¹. Table 1 presents selected features of 19 analyzed IS CIs. It shows significant differences in virtually all aspects of the methodology. We can find among them both studies, which are worth to promote (e.g. the ICT Development Index, cf. Goliński 2009), and tools in which the marketing aspect dominates over the substantive value (e.g. Networked Readiness Index, cf. Goliński 2010). Some of these tools have become quite popular and have gained a large group of proponents. However, we believe that this popularity is often undeserved.

One can also boldly assume that the IS CIs are in fact superfluous. If one assumes that the well-being of contemporary societies strongly correlates with the information and the ICT, then one also has to assume that the successful countries must have utilized both factors effectively. „Wherefore by

¹ OECD (2008: 100 and following) carried out a simulation of changes in the values of Technology Achievement Index. The differences in the positions of 23 first countries in the ranking reached 11 as a result of the various methods of weighting and aggregation.

their fruits ye shall know them”– if they are “wealthy”, they must also be “informational”. And in such case one does not need new tools, yet there is the GDP. This risky thesis is based on high correlation levels between IS development (measured by the ICT Development Index – IDI value) and prosperity (measured on the basis of: GDP – $r^2=0,55$ and HDI – $r^2=0,7$) in EU countries. The correlation does not mean that any causality relationship exists, but the problem itself seems to be worth looking into.

Table 1: Selected features of analyzed IS composite indices

Index	Author	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
ICT Development Index	ITU	2009	154	3	0	11	11	0	8	3
Connectivity Scorecard	Waverman	2009	50	6	0	28	28	0	28	0
ICT At-a-Glance	WB	2006	144	0	0	34	28	6	27	7
ICT Diffusion Index	UNCTAD	2006	180	2	0	8	8	0	6	2
ICT Opportunity Index	ITU	2007	183	2	2	10	10	0	8	2
Digital Opportunity Index	ITU	2007	181	3	0	11	11	0	11	0
eEurope 2005	INSEAD/SAP	2005	28	5	0	39	34	5	39	0
Knowledge Economy Index	WB	2008	140	4	0	12	9	3	3	9
Index of Knowledge Societies	UNPAN	2005	45	3	0	15	14	1	2	13
Net Readiness Perception Index	Goliński	2007	49	4	0	12	0	12	5	7
Digital Access Index	ITU	2003	178	5	0	8	8	0	6	2
Infostates	Orbicom/ITU	2007	183	2	2	10	10	0	8	2
E-Government Readiness Index	UNPAN	2008	182	3	0	8	8	0	6	2
Networked Readiness Index	WEF	2009	127	3	3	68	27	41	29	39
Mobile/Internet Index	ITU	2002	206	3	0	26	20	6	26	0
Technology Achievement Index	UNDP	2001	72	4	0	8	8	0	2	6
E-Readiness Index*	EIU/IBM	2008	70	6	0	100	50	50	20	80
Information Society Index	IDC	2008	53	4	0	15	13	2	11	4
II Development Level Index	Goliński	2004	29	0	0	7	7	0	7	0

Legend: (3) year of the last research, (4) number of countries in research (5) subindices, (6) subindices, II level, (7) partial indicators, including: (8) hard data, (9) soft data, (10) concerning ICT, (11) other *est.

4 Conclusions

CIs are good for making the public opinion aware of the gravity of IS issues. They do it well and in an impressive manner. However, if one is to make political or investment decisions one needs to perform a detailed, multi-criteria analysis using a set of numerous indicators. CIs should be considered as points of departure for policy-makers. They promote IS issues, yield arguments and help to shape development policy. Finally, although using these tools to analyse IS often constitutes an attempt to count the uncountable, one cannot dismiss the fact that CIs play a key role in promoting the vision of IS. By using CIs in IS analysis one should heed the old Russian proverb: “Trust, but verify”.

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